
Rights Of Refugees In India With Special Reference To Their Victimisation And Possible Solutions

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Abstract

Refugee is not just a term. It is an expression that can alter someone's life. It is a statement that, if once applied upon a person, renders him to the whims of a different power. A power with which he has no ethnic, social or national link. In other words, refugee is the metaphorical boundary, on one end of which lies security and on the other side lies a life of uncertainty & fear. A simple definition of the term "Refugee" means any person who has taken shelter. In more technical sense, Refugee would mean any person or group of persons who have left their native land and have taken shelter to other nation owing to several social, economic and political reasons. 'Refugees' have been a hot potato of Indian socio-political arena. While the natives fear them and consider them as a burden on the already deficient resources, which in fact leads to violence and other forms of victimisation of refugees, there is a section that perceives them as an addition to the already saturated amount of population whose inflow is likely to cause and sometimes causes law and order troubles. But, being run on the lines of socialism and democracy, a conflict from humanitarian perspective also arises. Many a times this conflict has reached to the judiciary. This paper provides an insight into the refugee issue from the Indian perspective and how refugees in India are victimised and the allied causes for it. The paper also ponders upon the possibilities of framing a refugee centric legislation as a possible solution to the refugee issue in India and how it can act as a medium to curb their victimisation.

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I. Introduction

On 2nd September, 2015; Alan Kurdi, a two-year-old boy, who had fled from Syria along with his family was found dead near the shores of the Mediterranean. The images of Alan Kurdi ignited an international debate. Debate regarding the refugee crisis that had been looming upon the world for a long time but, the world had kept its eyes closed like a pigeon to the cat that was already out of the hat. The conditions that the refugees had to face in day to day life and how they wanted to leave everything in order to get a peaceful life.

The international community had to turn its heads to the refugee problem. Despite having multifaceted conventions and underlying protections, the incident proved that the refugees were still the victims of the issues that these conventions that aimed to counter. It highlighted the fact that they were not considered a part of international conflict in practical terms and how they were being denied the basic human rights. The debate reached India as well. The nation had already seen the worst refugee crisis not just of the subcontinent alone, but the world. The nation had seen multiple influx of refugees right from its birth. Some of these influxes had turned violent and some became a threat to its internal security in the long run.

It is due to this reason that refugee crisis has always been perceived from the outlook of indigenous population and has been synonymous to threat such as terrorism. On having a look on this latter viewpoint, one can understand the Indian concern. Being in a dangerous neighbourhood and having a troubled history against terrorism, the fears appear to be rational. However, what is irrational is the fact that every foreigner who is blemished by conflict and wishes to take refuge in the nation is seen from that scope. This, sometimes culminates an aversion and hatred towards them. The result is violence, ostracization and other physical and psychological acts which pushes them to alienate themselves from the society.

There exists safeguards to the refugees under Indian Constitution but they are not specifically designed for refugees. They deal with foreigners which is assumed to have a self-explanatory meaning of refugees. This also leads to their victimisation as there exists no legal shield that guards them and them specifically.

II. International Perspective on Refugees

It was after the horrors of World War-II when the Jews were massively persecuted and had to flee to other nations to save their lives, the world community came together to ensure that any incident of this kind does not happen again and even if it happens, the people affected by it should not suffer. The establishment of United Nations Organisation on 24th October, 1945 was one such step. In a short span of five years several conventions were signed so that even in case of a mass conflict, the general population did not suffer. Amelioration of the Condition of the Wounded and Sick in Armed Forces in the Field, 1949; Geneva Convention Relative to the Treatment of Prisoner of War, 1949 Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflict, 1977 are some examples of such conventions.

One such convention was the Convention on the Status of Refugees, 1951. The Convention was important in the respect that it was the first attempt in world history to identify and define refugees and also to elaborate upon their rights and respective protection.

According to the Convention of 1951, a refugee can be defined as¹

“any person who as a result of events occurring before 1 January, 1951 and owing to well-founded fear of being persecuted for reasons of race, religions, nationality, membership of a particular social group or political opinion, is outside the country of his nationality and is unable or, owing to such fear, is unwilling to avail himself of the protection of that country; or who, not having a nationality and being outside the country of his former habitual residence as a result of such events, is unable or, owing to such fear, is unwilling to return to it”

This definition was significant because it had defined refugees for the first time. Further, it had broadened the scope of definition of refugees that were earlier only considered as displaced persons. The definition also gave impetus to other organisations to define refugees who considered this definition either to be incomplete or having its roots in the past. Further modifications on the definition of refugees were done by the Protocol Relating to Status of Refugees, 1967.

¹ B.S. Chimni (ed.), *International Refugee Law A reader 2* (Sage Publications, New Delhi, 2000).

The Protocol removed the temporal and geographical limitations contained in the 1951 Convention². Several other conventions such as the “1969 OAU Convention Governing the Specific Aspects of Refugee Problems in Africa” and the “Cartagena Declaration on Refugees, 1964” also helped in expanding the sphere of the term ‘Refugees’ to give it a broad outlook. The worth of this expansion was that refugee became an all-encompassing concept whose horizons broadened enough to engulf within it every individual marred by conflict and owing to such conflict is succumbed to leave his homeland.

III. Legal Perspective on Refugees in India

India is not a party to the 1951 Refugee Convention or its 1967 Protocol and does not have a national refugee protection framework. However, it continues to grant asylum to a large number of refugees from neighbouring States and respects UNHCR’s mandate for other nationals, mainly from Afghanistan and Myanmar.³ India has had the policy of applying its municipal laws on foreigners and has in a way immune itself from any international law that might hinder its suzerainty when deciding the matters in relation to foreigners.

However, this does not mean that India has alienated itself from Human Rights issues. It is a party to United Nations International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), 1966 and 1966 Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights.⁴ Also, it is a party to Convention on the Rights of Child, 1989. Largely, the Foreigners Act, 1946 and the Registration of Foreigners Act, 1939 deal with foreign nationals in India. In addition to them Registration of Foreigners Rules, 1992 also assists in foreign nationals’ regulation in India. Additionally, the Indian Citizenship Act, 1955 also deals with certain aspects of foreign national. But these are too narrow in nature to encompass refugees and consider and treat refugees as foreigners, which in international practices are two separate entities.

² *Ibid.* at 7.

³ GA_2011_Asia.vp available at: <https://www.unhcr.org/4cd96e919.pdf> (Visited on March 5, 2023).

⁴ *Supra* note 1 at 484.

IV. Constitutional Stance on Refugees

The term “refugee” does not find a mention in the Indian Constitution. However, the word “Alien” appears in the Constitution under two provisions. Firstly, under Article 22 (3) and secondly, under List-I Entry 17 of the VII Schedule.⁵ Also, some of the Fundamental Rights guaranteed under Part III of the Constitution shall be available to all persons and hence, they are available to refugees as well.⁶ This means, right to equality under Article-14, Right to protection in respect of conviction of offences under Article-20, Right to life and personal liberty under Article 21 and Right to protection against arrest and detention under Article 22 is available to refugees in India.

V. Indian Judiciary on Refugees in India

There have been many judicial pronouncements regarding refugees and their condition in India. Though, it did not expressly mention the term ‘foreigner’; a simple deduction would suffice that it referred to refugees as well. In 1984, the Supreme Court of India gave a verdict whereby it stated that despite the fact that India is a party to international covenants and many aspects of international law are binding upon the nation. But, in case of any conflict the supremacy of law-making power of legislature cannot be subdued by any international mechanism. It did, however say that international law’s rules can be incorporated into national laws but if there is a conflict, municipal laws are to prevail.⁷

This view was somehow modified into a less stern stance by the apex Court in *Kubic Dariusz v. Union of India*⁸, whereby the Supreme Court called for a harmonising relationship between Municipal laws and international covenants. It stated that it is true that the national legal system would cover the matters pertaining to foreigners within India but such laws must be interpreted keeping in mind the international obligations of the nation. Similarly, the Supreme Court in *Louis De Raedt v. Union of India*⁹ pronounced that the rights available under the Indian Constitution are available to foreigners as well.

⁵ The Constitution of India, 1950.

⁶ Dr. H.O. Agarwal, *International Law & Human Rights* 877 (Central Law Publications, Allahabad, 20th edn., 2014).

⁷ *Gramophone Co. of India v. Birendra Bahadur Pandey* (AIR 1984 SC 667).

⁸ AIR 1990 SC 605.

⁹ (1991) 3 SCC 554.

However, this should be seen in the light that not all the rights are available to the foreigners. There are several rights that are expressly mentioned in the Indian Constitution to be available to citizens only. Thus, equality of opportunity in matters of public employment guaranteed under Article-16 is not available to foreigners but, the protection of life and personal liberty available under Article-21 is available as the latter's plain reading would suffice that it is available to "all persons".

A landmark verdict securing basic human rights of refugees on India came in *National Human Rights Commission v. State of Arunachal Pradesh*¹⁰ whereby the court reiterated that India is a state that is governed by Rule of Law. It added that it was the duty of the state to provide certain fundamental rights provided under various provisions of the Constitution of India viz. Article 14 and Article 21. The Supreme Court perhaps mentioned refugees for the first time when in the case of *Malavika Karlekar vs. Union of India*¹¹, it ordered the stay of Myanmar refugees on Andaman Islands since their application for refugee status was still pending and till their status was decided, they cannot be expelled.

VI. Victimisation of Refugees in India

Victimisation is not an isolated concept. Like a demon it has many forms and shapes. The goliath of human rights, victimisation can be termed as an act which renders a person to the whims of unjust treatment. In India, victimisation is not a well-developed concept *per se* and consequently, refugee victimisation has been one of those legal areas that are dormant to say the least. However, certain heads can be put into perspective to get a broader outlook as to how refugees are victimised in India.

A. Violence Against Refugees: Usually, refugees are considered alien to the local civilisation. They are considered to be outsiders that have inhabited the land and may "disturb" it. Any non-conformity to the local rules may result into an exchange of words and then turn ugly. Several incidents have borne the testimony to this fact.

B. Ostracising of Refugees: The native population considers refugees and the local population as chalk & cheese. They are not considered to be part of the traditional line-up irrespective of the fact that how much homogenous they are in terms of culture, social practices and ancestry.

¹⁰ AIR 1996 SC 1234.

¹¹ Writ Petition (Criminal No) 583 OF 1992.

The example of Chakma Refugees best fits this situation. Several NGOs in the hill state of Mizoram recently demanded that the Chakma refugees be denied voting rights in the Assembly elections. Young Mizo Association- the largest of these NGOs held rallies across the state in this regard.¹² This might seem to be a legitimate demand but, the Chakma refugees have been living in the region for past 50 years or more. Several generations of these refugees have passed and the current generation is eligible for citizenship in accordance with the Indian laws.

C. *Hate Comments:* Hate comments against refugee population does not affect them in tangible manner but its effects are intangible. They supplement the fears that the population is already stewing in. It makes their already uncertain life more ambiguous.

D. *Blaming Refugees on the Failure of Law and Order:* Refugees are often considered to be the cause of any disruption of law and order in a territory. This makes them vulnerable to any retaliation by locals who might seek “revenge” or be subject to mob violence. However, this, in itself is an antithesis. Firstly, the refugees are itself a creation of failure of law and order in their state and were a victim to it and not a party. Secondly, even if it is considered that they had a role to play in the disruption of law and order of the territory, they are accordingly prosecuted and punished as per the municipal law like any other citizen. Blaming an entire community for the acts done by a few creates an anti-community sentiment and the refugees are seen from the spectacles of a deviant and the portal of any consequent help to them is closed from the end of the citizens.

E. *Xenophobia:* Xenophobia means a fear or hatred that stems from anything that is foreign. From sociological point of view, Xenophobia in this case would lie on the side of the native population and not the one who has come in. But a careful analysis would authenticate that it is perhaps the biggest source of victimisation of refugees. This works in a chain. Xenophobia compels masses to maintain an aversion to the refugees. The refugees that are then subject to aversion are alienated from society. Due to this alienation the local population considers them different from themselves that further aggravates the situation.

¹² Mizoram Polls: Mizos’ demand that Chakma candidates be denied tickets gets ignored by Congress, BJP, *available at:* <https://www.firstpost.com/politics/mizoram-polls-mizos-demand-that-chakma-candidates-be-denied-tickets-gets-ignored-by-congress-bjp-5512391.html> (Last Modified November 8, 2018).

This alienation closes the economic prospects for them. Lacking economic prospects, some turn deviant and commit offences like theft. This creates a further aversion in the minds of the native population that then considers them the greatest threat to local peace and security. This in turn, becomes the community rhetoric that is garnered by the politically motivated to collect some masses. This becomes a regional issue and then a national issue and the root cause for it lies in the fear of the foreign; leaving the innocent, non-deviant and usually economically poor as the real victims with no access to resources, community togetherness and constant fear of uprooted settlements leading to an uncertain future.

F. Harassment by Authorities: Often, the refugees that come to India are subject to constant questioning and bureaucratic hurdles. The process of gaining refugee status is very cumbersome and full of procedures. Also, a large part of this process is left to the discretion of the officer. Furthermore, the existing laws sometimes impose troubles on refugees. For instance, Sec-3 of the Foreigners Act, 1946 provides that the authorities can issue Leave India Notices to such people who have failed to satisfactorily register themselves with authorities.¹³ Thus, the refugees are at the mercy of these authorities and can be forcefully deported adding further to the mental trauma of uncertainties regarding their future.

VII. Suggestions

All the factors mentioned above are the catalysts to the existing refugee problem in India. There exists a cause effect relationship in refugee victimisation that, if halted, can ensure a secure future for refugees. The 1951 Convention does talk about the rights of the refugees and some often argue that these are sure enough provisions for controlling their victimisation. But, this cannot be applied in Indian context because firstly, mere conferment of rights do not guarantee protection until or unless there is an enforcing agency and secondly, India not being a signatory to the 1951 convention, is not bound to accept its provisions.

¹³ The Foreigners Act, 1946 (Act 31 of 1946).

However, there lie multiple solutions to this problem of refugee victimisation in India.

A. Enactment of a Law dedicated to Refugees:

Neither is India a party to the 1951 Convention nor it has a law dedicated to refugees. As mentioned earlier, it has various Acts that deal with Foreigners but they do not encompass the term 'refugee' in them. Presence of a municipal law that talks about refugees would secure their rights and help in preventing refugee victimisation in India. When a legal protection is available to an individual or group of individuals; it gives them a security. A security from the fear that there is an imminent danger to their life and property in the new state.

B. Establishment of National Centre for Refugees:

A national level centre for refugees can be established on the lines of UNHCR. This would act as an enforcing agency and can help in regulating refugees in India in terms of their security and ensure the access to basic amenity to them. This centre can work with the UNHCR, the Ministry of External Affairs and the Ministry of Defence to get a holistic coverage of refugee issue in India.

C. Record of Refugees:

An e-record of refugees can be established. The e-record would be a part of Refugee Status Determination (RSD) procedures and shall be done in accordance with international standards. The record can be an inclusive document that contains their educational qualifications, skills and previous jobs. This would help the authorities to know the status of refugees in India and thus, it can enact an effective policy considering the social, economic and ethnic conditions of the refugees. Furthermore, it shall help the refugees as well since they shall be able to get a recognised identity in a State that sometimes does not even acknowledge their presence. Also, it shall help them in their systematic repatriation.

D. Regulating Refugee Shelters:

A regulation on refugee shelters should be done. Regulation does not mean policing. It means that they should be checked at regular intervals so as to ensure that no deviant entity is entering the shelters. Also, it can help in controlling many allied modes of refugee victimisation such as drug abuse amongst the refugees and physical and mental cruelty inflicted upon them by the local population.

E. Spreading Awareness among the Local Populace:

Citizens should be informed about the rights of the refugees. They must be counselled about the circumstances that the refugees have gone through and an attempt to create empathy in favour of refugees must be made. In this regard, civil society, NGOs and the government alike can join hands. This would help removing xenophobia and would reduce violence against the refugees that is usually at the behest of the local population which considers them as outsiders.

F. Avenues of Employment:

New avenues of employment can be opened up for refugees. Several employment schemes like the Skill India Development Scheme and Make in India scheme can be made all-inclusive to cover refugees within their ambit. This would, in fact, assist refugees to have economic sustainability and they can also become a part of human resource of the nation.

G. Increase the Ambit of Social Security Schemes and Programmes:

Several social security schemes such as the Ayushman Bharat Yojana and the *Swawalamban Scheme* includes people of India. They provide social security benefit to the population. However, there are certain kinds of refugees in India who have been living in India for past two to three generations but do not fall under any of these schemes on account of void of citizenship. There can be a new social security scheme targeted towards refugees or the existing schemes can be broadened enough to include them so as to widen the umbrella of basic amenities that are to be granted to refugees under several international Protocols and Conventions. Although it must be noted that none of the above solutions can single-handedly solve the issue of refugee victimisation in India. All these factors along with the intent of the organs of the State is needed to tackle this issue.

VIII. Conclusion

It needs to be understood that refugees are not only a mere group of people who have entered a nation just because they could not live into their own. They must be viewed from humanitarian point of view. They must be viewed for the spectacles of those people who survived a human tragedy and came into a land that, according to them, and according to their current circumstances, was heaven. They should not and cannot be viewed as citizens of the nation but should also not to be seen as outsiders. They must be considered a part of the family. A part of the “*Vasudheva Kutumbkam*”. India has been a land of tolerance and acceptance. It has had that stance even before the birth of modern nations. India still has many refugees within its territory that are victimised on a daily basis either physically in forms of violence or psychologically in the form of irrational threats and statements directed towards them. The situation calls for action. Action on the part of government and citizens alike. The solution lies in framing a piece of legislation that defines refugees, elaborates their rights, enumerates their duties and lays down protocol for their repatriation. It is a collective effort that can only progenote from the conscience of the State and the masses alike. As mentioned, refugees are to be viewed from humanitarian perspective. They are to be seen as survivors of a horror, that have been subjected to another.